

Analysis of Cultural Factors at Santo Thomas 2 Medan Catholic Private Elementary School, 2022/2023 Academic Year

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ABSTRACT

This research aims to analyze school cultural factors at the Santo Thomas 2 Medan Catholic Private Elementary School. The method used in this research is qualitative with a case study approach, with data collection in the form of interviews, observation and documentation. The results of this research show that so far the implementation of school culture at the Santo Thomas 2 Medan Catholic Private Elementary School has been implemented well. There are several things that can support the successful implementation of school culture, including the existing infrastructure at the Santo Thomas 2 Medan Catholic Private Elementary School which is quite complete and adequate, the role of parents who provide support in the form of material support (students' needs) and non-material support (in the form of love, attention, responsibility, enthusiasm and motivation) for students, by creating a conducive environment can be a supporting factor in the successful implementation of school culture, forming disciplined and focused school management can support the success of business culture, the attitude of students who are active in carrying out activities that blend school culture and the attitudes of teachers who have discipline and responsibility in implementing school culture.

INTRODUCTION

Based on the information obtained, researchers found that there is a school culture that is based on Don Bosco's Catholic values, so that the Santo Thomas 2 Medan Catholic Private Elementary School has its own values and characteristics that make the school different from other elementary schools. The school culture is based on Don Bosco's Catholic values, including: (a) cooperation, (b) caring, (c) responsibility, (d) attention, (e) forgiveness and compassion, (h) respect for others, (i) gentleness, (j) humility, (k) friendliness, (l) sharing with others, (m) friendship, (n) courtesy, (o) tolerance. And Don Bosco's Catholic values have been implemented in daily habits in the school environment.

LITERATURE REVIEW

1. Collaboration is an attitude of wanting to do work together without looking at the background of the person being collaborated with to achieve a goal.
2. Collaboration is an attitude of wanting to do work together without looking at the background of the person being collaborated with to achieve a goal.
3. Responsibility is carrying out all duties and obligations seriously.
4. Attention is an activity carried out by a person in solving the selection of stimuli that come from the environment.
5. Compassion is to bear with another person, to put ourselves in the other person's shoes, to feel his suffering as if it were our own and to generously enter into his point of view.
6. Respect is respecting others by acting kindly and politely. Respect is the virtue that underlies good manners.
7. Meekness is being strong, not weak; active, not passive; brave, not shy; controlled, not excessive; simple, not arrogant; and be virtuous, not rude. A meek person is not easily provoked, pretentious, or arrogant and readily acknowledges the achievements of others.
8. Hospitality is offering a sense of belonging to everyone. Friendliness creates a warm environment.
9. Sharing is an action where we give what we have to other people who need it.
10. Manners mean rules of life that arise from the interaction of a group of people in society and are considered to be the demands of that society's daily interactions.
11. Tolerance means respecting individuals and their differences, removing the masks and tensions caused by indifference

METHODOLOGY

The method I use in this approach is a qualitative research method with a case study approach. The data analysis technique that I use is by conducting observations, interviews and documentation in the field. The informants I interviewed when conducting research in the field consisted of school principals, teachers and students.

RESEARCH RESULT

The research results that I found in the field were that the Santo Thomas 2 Medan Catholic Private Elementary School had school cultural values that were based on Don Bosco's Catholic values, including (a) cooperation, (b) caring, (c) responsibility, (d) attention, (e) forgiveness and compassion, (h) respect for others, (i) gentleness, (j) humility, (k) friendliness, (l) sharing with others, (m) friendship, (n) courtesy, (o) tolerance.

DISCUSSION

Based on the results of research in the field, so far all school members have implemented a culture in the school environment based on Don Bosco's Catholic values, including: (a) the attitude of cooperation in the school environment has been implemented well, it can be seen from all school members working together. in maintaining the cleanliness of the school environment both inside and outside the classroom, working together in participating in school cultural activities such as religious activities (rosary prayers, mass) as well as participating in morning gymnastics and other activities. (b) the school has also implemented a caring attitude carried out by all school members, such as carrying out fasting and food demonstrations, caring for each other regarding the cleanliness of the school environment, caring for each other between teachers and students at school, (c) as for the form of an attitude of responsibility responsibilities that have been implemented in schools, namely the attitude of teachers as educators who have a good attitude of responsibility in teaching and educating students at school, (d) as well as an attitude of mutual respect between teachers and principals, teachers and students and students and their colleagues. has been implemented well, (e) the school community has so far implemented an attitude of sharing in the school environment, it can be seen from the attitude of teachers who share knowledge in the world of education, and the attitude of sharing that is developed by students in school, namely in various ways. food or sharing knowledge when carrying out group work activities (discussions) during classroom learning, (f) polite attitudes at school have been implemented by all school members, especially students, because students have implemented the 5S attitude (smile, polite, greeting, courteous) to the principal, teachers, and other students at school, (g) the last is an attitude of tolerance where this attitude has been implemented in the environment through the culture that exists in the school, such as respecting differences, accepting other people's opinions and carry out deliberations with the entire school community in realizing the school's vision and mission which is based on Don Bosco's Catholic values.

CONCLUSIONS AND RECOMMENDATIONS

Based on the research results that have been described through analysis and descriptive chapter IV referring to the problem formulation, it can be concluded that the school culture that has been implemented at the Santo Thomas 2 Medan Catholic Private Elementary School is based on Don Dosco's

Catholic values, namely (a) cooperation, (b) care, (c) responsibility, (d) attention, (e) forgiveness and compassion, (h) respect for others, (i) gentleness, (j) humility, (k) friendliness, (l) sharing with others, (m) friendly, (n) polite, (o) tolerance. And so far researchers have observed that the school culture is running well in the school environment

ADVANCED RESEARCH

Apart from that, the results of the research above, there are several recommendations (suggestions) that the author provides, including:

1. The principal supports teachers in implementing school culture and provides complete school facilities to support the implementation of school culture well.
2. Teachers as educators must be able to shape the character of students through habituating attitudes and behavior that contain school values and norms. Apart from that, teachers must also set a good example for their students.
3. Students are expected to participate in teaching and learning activities well and obey school regulations, both written and unwritten.
4. For future researchers, they can carry out the same research but on different subjects and schools regarding school culture in developing students' religious character.

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The research limitations consist of:

1. This research was carried out since October 2023. During this time, the researcher tried to understand and involve himself in various activities at school. Therefore, the aspects that were successfully revealed in this research process occurred from March 2023 to November 2023. Before and after this time are not of concern to researchers, so it is very possible that changes have occurred that were not recorded in this research
2. The research subjects observed in this study were the principal, deputy principal, teachers and students. The attitudes and behavior of research subjects when in the classroom cannot be observed directly. Thus, the information obtained is only limited to information and data that is outside the classroom or on the school grounds, so it is very possible that research subjects behave differently when in the classroom and researchers cannot reveal comprehensive research processes and results.

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